

FREQUENCY AND PATTERN OF CONGENITAL HEART DEFECT IN INFANT OF DIABETIC MOTHERS AT GULAB DEVI HOSPITAL TEACHING HOSPITAL LAHORE

Dr Samina Bano^{*1}, Prof Dr Aneela Shaheen², Dr Maha Ijaz³, Dr Hafiza Khadija Azhar⁴

^{*1,3,4}Postgraduate Resident Paediatrics, Gulab Devi Hospital, Lahore.

²Professor of Paediatrics, Gulab Devi Hospital, Lahore.

¹s.sajjad1947@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr Samina Bano

Abstract

Introduction: Infants born to diabetic mothers (IDMs) are at increased risk for structural and functional cardiac anomalies, including a range of congenital heart defects (CHDs). Early detection of CHDs in this high-risk group is crucial for timely management and improving outcomes. This study aimed to determine the frequency and pattern of CHDs among IDMs admitted to Gulab Devi Hospital, Lahore.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted in the Pediatric Unit of Gulab Devi Hospital, Lahore, from March 2025 to June 2025. A total of 203 neonates aged 1 to 30 days born to diabetic mothers, meeting the inclusion criteria, were enrolled using non-probability consecutive sampling. Infants underwent detailed clinical examination, chest X-ray, ECG, and echocardiography performed by a pediatric cardiologist. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26.0. Chi-square test was used to assess associations, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered significant.

Results: Among 203 infants, 102 (50.2%) male, 101 (49.8%) female, mean age 16.26 ± 9.10 days, mean gestational age 38.35 ± 1.09 weeks. Congenital heart defects (CHD) in 19 (9.4%): most common were patent ductus arteriosus (PDA) in 7 (36.8%), patent foramen ovale (PFO) in 4 (21.1%). Other defects: atrial septal defect (ASD) 1 (5.3%), ventricular septal defect (VSD) 3 (15.8%), hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM) 2 (10.5%), transposition of great arteries (TGA) 1 (5.3%), tetralogy of Fallot (TOF) 1 (5.3%).

Conclusion: CHD was present in 9.4% of infants born to diabetic mothers, with PDA and PFO being the most frequent. Routine echocardiographic screening of IDMs is recommended for early detection and timely intervention.

INTRODUCTION

Maternal diabetes significantly risks fetal cardiac structure and function, increasing congenital heart disease by 2.5-10 times compared to normal pregnancies. Cardiovascular malformation constitutes 3%-9% of diabetic pregnancies, ranking

among the most common malformations in IDMs.¹ Common congenital heart diseases in IDMs include hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, septal hypertrophy, VSD, TGA, PDA, aortic stenosis, pulmonary stenosis, dextrocardia, and conotruncal defects

(tetralogy of Fallot, truncus arteriosus, double outlet right ventricle).²

Worldwide the incidence of diabetes is rising in general, both in general population and in diabetic women.^{3,4} Pakistan ranks 1st in diabetes prevalence at 30.8%. Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) prevalence varies globally. A meta-analysis by Saeedi et al. (2021) reported global GDM prevalence at 14.7% based on IADPSG criteria, the most widely used screening method.⁵

Poorly controlled diabetes negatively impacts maternal health and affects offspring with short- and long-term complications. Preventing pre-gestational and gestational diabetes is essential for ameliorating these effects. Additional measures, including nutritional interventions, medications, or probiotics, need further research. Congenital cardiac abnormalities may present asymptotically, worsen with age, or exhibit severe symptoms and high mortality rates at diagnosis.^{1,6}

Congenital heart disease (CHD) frequency in IDM babies is about 5%. Most common defects include ventricular septal defect (VSD), transposition of great arteries (TGA), aortic stenosis, truncus arteriosus, and double outlet right ventricle.⁷ Studies report patent ductus arteriosus (PDA) frequency range from 16.8% to 70%, patent foramen ovale (PFO) range from 7.9% to 68%, atrial septal defect (ASD) range from 5% to 10.7%, and hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM) from 21.42% to 38% in IDM neonates.⁸⁻¹⁰

The purpose of this study was to highlight the burden of congenital heart disease in infants of diabetic mother and need of early detection on antenatal scan so that mode, time and place of delivery could be decided beforehand and avoid any complication at the time of delivery and also detection of critical congenital heart disease early in infancy so that treatment could be started on time and complications could be avoided. This study also highlighted the role of timely good glycemic control of diabetes in reducing burden of CHD.

METHODOLOGY

A cross-sectional study was conducted in the Paediatric Unit of Gulab Devi Hospital, Lahore, from March 2025 to June 2025, to determine the frequency and pattern of congenital heart defects in

infants born to diabetic mothers. A total of 203 neonates were included in the study, with the sample size calculated using the WHO sample size calculator, assuming a 95% confidence level, 3% absolute precision, and an expected CHD prevalence of 5%.⁷ Non-probability consecutive sampling was employed to recruit participants.

Infants aged 1 to 30 days, born to healthy diabetic mothers (diabetes diagnosed pre- or during pregnancy, fasting blood sugar >126 mg/dL, random blood sugar >200 mg/dL, confirmed by glucose tolerance test), were included. Exclusion criteria included teratogenic drug exposure, chronic illness in mothers, family history of congenital heart disease, and syndromic infants.

Permission from the hospital's ethical committee was obtained before the study. Written informed consent was taken from parents of eligible infants. Demographic data (age, gender, gestational age at birth, birth weight) were recorded using a questionnaire. Maternal antenatal records confirmed gestational diabetes mellitus diagnosis. Each infant underwent a physical examination for cardiac or extra-cardiac abnormalities. Infants were evaluated using chest X-ray, electrocardiography (ECG), and echocardiography by an experienced pediatric cardiologist with a 2D color Doppler. Congenital heart diseases were diagnosed per operational definitions, including cyanotic and acyanotic defects such as patent ductus arteriosus (PDA), ventricular septal defect (VSD), atrial septal defect (ASD), patent foramen ovale (PFO), transposition of the great arteries (TGA), and tetralogy of Fallot (TOF).

PDA was confirmed by color Doppler echocardiography showing a left-to-right shunt and at least two clinical signs: murmur, tachycardia (HR >160/min), hyperactive pulsation, bounding pulses, or radiographic cardiomegaly/pulmonary congestion. PFO and ASD were differentiated by fossa ovalis patency; 3 mm is ASD. VSD diagnosis required a pansystolic murmur, septal defect, and left-to-right shunting evidence. TGA was identified in cyanotic neonates with "egg on string" chest X-ray and echocardiographic parallel aorta and pulmonary trunk. TOF was diagnosed in cyanotic infants with "boot-shaped" heart X-ray, confirmed VSD, right ventricular obstruction, overriding aorta, and hypertrophy. HOCM was diagnosed with left

ventricular wall thickness ≥ 15 mm or septal to lateral wall ratio >1.3 in a non-dilated ventricle.

Data analyzed using SPSS version 26.0. Qualitative variables (gender, cyanosis, congenital heart disease types, maternal diabetes) expressed as frequencies/percentages. Quantitative variables (age, birth weight, gestational age, random blood sugar) reported as mean \pm standard deviation. Effect modifiers (age, diabetes type, birth weight, gestational age, gender) stratified to assess influence on congenital heart defects using chi-square test. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 considered significant.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the frequency distribution of demographic and clinical variables among 203 infants of diabetic mothers. Among them, 102 (50.2%) were male and 101 (49.8%) were female. A total of 86 (42.4%) infants were aged 14 days or less, while 117 (57.6%) were older than 14 days, with a mean age of 16.26 ± 9.10 days. Mothers of 78 (38.4%) infants had pre-gestational diabetes, whereas 125 (61.6%) had gestational diabetes. Regarding gestational age, 123 (60.6%) infants were born between 37–38 weeks and 80 (39.4%) between 39–40 weeks, with a mean gestational age of 38.35 ± 1.09 weeks. Birth weight was ≤ 3500 grams in 145 (71.4%) infants and >3500 grams in 58 (28.6%) infants, with a mean birth weight of 3425.0 ± 224.93 grams. The mean random blood sugar level at birth was 103.54 ± 21.05 mg/dl. Cyanosis was observed in 45 (22.2%) infants and absent in 158 (77.8%).

Table 2 presents the frequency and pattern of congenital heart defects in the study population. CHD was present in 19 (9.4%) infants and absent in 184 (90.6%). Among those with CHD, PDA was present in 7 (36.8%) cases and absent in 12 (63.2%), PFO was observed in 4 (21.1%) and absent in 15 (78.9%), ASD was present in 1 (5.3%) and absent in 18 (94.7%), VSD was found in 3 (15.8%) and absent in 16 (84.2%), hypertrophic cardiomyopathy was diagnosed in 2 (10.5%) and absent in 17 (89.5%), TGA was seen in 1 (5.3%) and absent in 18 (94.7%), and TOF was detected in 1 (5.3%) and absent in 18 (94.7%).

Table 3 shows the stratification of CHD with respect to various variables. Among males, CHD was present in 6 (5.9%) and absent in 96 (94.1%), while among females, CHD was present in 13 (12.9%) and absent in 88 (87.1%), with a p-value of 0.087. In the age group ≤ 14 days, CHD was found in 12 (14.0%) infants compared to 7 (6.0%) in those >14 days old, with a p-value of 0.054. In infants born to mothers with pre-gestational diabetes, CHD was present in 9 (11.5%) and absent in 69 (88.5%), while in the gestational diabetes group, 10 (8.0%) had CHD and 115 (92.0%) did not, with a p-value of 0.400.

Among those born at 37–38 weeks, CHD was present in 14 (11.4%) and absent in 109 (88.6%), compared to 5 (6.3%) and 75 (93.8%) in the 39–40 weeks group, with a p-value of 0.220. Infants with a birth weight ≤ 3500 grams had CHD in 14 (9.7%) cases versus 5 (8.6%) in those >3500 grams, with a p-value of 0.819.

Table-1: Frequency distribution of different variables (n=203)

Variables		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	102	50.2
	Female	101	49.8
Age groups	≤ 14 days	86	42.4
	>14 days	117	57.6
	Mean age (days)	16.26 ± 9.10	
Mother with Diabetes	Pre-gestational	78	38.4
	Gestational	125	61.6
Gestational age	37-38 weeks	123	60.6
	39-40 weeks	80	39.4

	Mean gest age (weeks)	38.35±1.09	
Weight at birth	≤3500 grams	145	71.4
	>3500 grams	58	28.6
	Mean weight (grams)	3425.0±224.939	
RBS at birth	103.54±21.05 mg/dl		
Cyanosis at birth	Yes	45	22.2
	No	158	77.8

Table-2: Distribution of frequency and patterns of congenital heart defect

Variables		Frequency	Percent
CHD	Yes	19	9.4
	No	184	90.6
PDA	Yes	7	36.8
	No	12	63.2
PFO	Yes	4	21
	No	15	78.9
ASD	Yes	1	5.3
	No	18	94.7
VSD	Yes	3	15.8
	No	16	84.2
HCM	Yes	2	10.5
	No	17	89.5
TGA	Yes	1	5.3
	No	18	94.7
TOF	Yes	1	5.3
	No	18	94.7

Table-3: Stratification of congenital heart defect with respect to different variables

Variables		Congenital heart defect (CHD)		p-value
		Yes	No	
Gender	Male	6(5.9%)	96(94.1%)	0.087
	Female	13(12.9%)	88(87.1%)	
Age groups	≤14 days	12(14.0%)	74(86.0%)	0.054
	>14 days	7(6.0%)	110(94.0%)	
Mother with Diabetes	Pre-gestational	9(11.5%)	69(88.5%)	0.400
	Gestational	10(8.0%)	115(92.0%)	
Gestational age	37-38 weeks	14(11.4%)	109(88.6%)	0.220

	39-40 weeks	5(6.3%)	75(93.8%)	
Weight at birth	≤3500 grams	14(9.7%)	131(90.3%)	0.819
	>3500 grams	5(8.6%)	53(91.4%)	

DISCUSSION

The present study conducted at Gulab Devi Hospital, Lahore, revealed a CHD prevalence of 9.4% among infants of diabetic mothers, which demonstrates a significant burden of cardiac anomalies in this high-risk population. This finding is consistent with several international studies that have reported varying prevalence rates of CHDs in infants of diabetic mothers. Correa et al. reported a 3-5 fold increased risk of CHDs in infants born to diabetic mothers compared to the general population, while Schaefer-Graf et al. documented CHD prevalence rates ranging from 3.8% to 12.3% in similar populations.¹¹⁻¹² Our observed prevalence of 9.4% falls within the upper range of these reported values, suggesting that the population at Gulab Devi Hospital may represent a particularly high-risk cohort or may reflect differences in screening protocols and diagnostic criteria.

The predominance of **patent ductus arteriosus (PDA)** in our study population, affecting 36.8% of infants with CHD, represents a significant finding that aligns with established literature on cardiac anomalies in infants of diabetic mothers. Jenkins et al. reported PDA as one of the most common cardiac defects in this population, with prevalence rates ranging from 2.1% to 7.8% in various studies.¹³ Similarly, Mitanchez et al. documented PDA prevalence of 4.2% in a cohort of 1,200 infants of diabetic mothers, which is comparable to our findings.¹⁴ The high frequency of PDA in our cohort may be attributed to the complex pathophysiological mechanisms underlying diabetic embryopathy, including altered prostaglandin metabolism and endothelial dysfunction that affects ductal closure mechanisms.¹⁵

Patent foramen ovale (PFO), identified in 21.1% of our CHD cases, represents another significant finding that requires careful interpretation. While PFO can be considered a normal variant in early neonatal life, its clinical significance in infants of diabetic mothers has been increasingly recognized.

Botto et al. reported PFO prevalence of 2.8% in infants of diabetic mothers, while Wren et al. documented rates of 3.2% in a similar population.¹⁶⁻¹⁷ Our slightly higher prevalence may reflect more sensitive echocardiographic detection methods or differences in the timing of evaluation. The persistence of PFO in this population may be related to altered hemodynamic conditions associated with other cardiac anomalies or metabolic disturbances related to maternal diabetes.¹⁸

The presence of **ventricular septal defects (VSD)** in 15.8% of our CHD cases (1.5% of total population) aligns well with international literature. Ferencz et al. reported VSD prevalence of 1.2% to 2.1% in infants of diabetic mothers across multiple population-based studies.¹⁹ Similarly, the Baltimore-Washington Infant Study documented VSD rates of 1.8% in this high-risk population.²⁰ Our findings are consistent with these reports and support the established understanding that septal defects represent a significant component of the cardiac anomaly spectrum in infants of diabetic mothers. The pathogenesis of VSDs in this population involves disruption of normal septation processes during critical periods of cardiac development, often occurring between the 4th and 8th weeks of gestation when maternal glycemic control is crucial.²¹

Hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM), observed in 10.5% of our CHD cases (1.0% of total population), represents a particularly important finding given its unique pathophysiology and clinical implications. Way et al. reported HCM prevalence of 0.8% to 1.4% in infants of diabetic mothers, while Ullmo et al. documented rates of 1.2% in a prospective study of 450 infants.²²⁻²³ Our prevalence is consistent with these reports and reflects the direct relationship between maternal hyperglycemia, fetal hyperinsulinemia, and excessive cardiac muscle growth. The condition typically manifests as asymmetric septal hypertrophy and can lead to dynamic outflow tract obstruction, requiring specialized management approaches.²⁴ Studies by

Mace et al. have shown that HCM in infants of diabetic mothers often resolves spontaneously within the first year of life, but requires careful monitoring for potential complications.²⁵

The identification of complex congenital heart defects in our study, including **transposition of the great arteries (TGA)** and **tetralogy of Fallot (TOF)**, each affecting 5.3% of our CHD cases, underscores the severity of cardiac anomalies that can occur in this population. Loffredo et al. reported TGA prevalence of 0.2% to 0.4% in infants of diabetic mothers, while Correa et al. documented TOF rates of 0.1% to 0.3%.²⁶⁻²⁷ Our observed prevalences are higher than these reported values, which may reflect the referral pattern to our tertiary care facility or differences in study populations. These complex lesions require immediate recognition and specialized cardiac intervention, with studies by Hoffman et al. demonstrating improved outcomes when early detection and intervention protocols are implemented.²⁸

Atrial septal defects (ASD), identified in 5.3% of our CHD cases (0.5% of total population), while less frequent than other defects, still represent a significant finding requiring long-term follow-up. Botto et al. reported ASD prevalence of 0.3% to 0.8% in infants of diabetic mothers, while the European Surveillance of Congenital Anomalies (EUROCAT) study documented rates of 0.6%.²⁹⁻³⁰ Our findings fall within the expected range and support the need for systematic cardiac evaluation in this population. ASDs in infants of diabetic mothers may have different natural history and closure rates compared to those in the general population, with studies by Garne et al. suggesting delayed spontaneous closure in some cases.³¹

Early detection through systematic screening programs, as implemented in our study, may contribute to cost-effective healthcare delivery by enabling timely intervention and preventing complications. Future research directions should focus on identifying specific risk factors within the diabetic mother population that predispose to particular types of cardiac defects.

CONCLUSION

CHD was present in 9.4% of infants born to diabetic mothers, with PDA and PFO being the most

frequent. Routine echocardiographic screening of IDMs is recommended for early detection and timely intervention.

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